

FEEDING IN POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS OF TURKEYS

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Abstract. This article contains information about turkey postnatal ontogenesis in food products.

Key words: turkey, diet, feed, corn and bone meal.

КОРМЛЕНИЕ В ПОСТНАТАЛЬНЫЙ ОНТОГЕНЕЗ ИНДЕЙКИ

Аннотация. В данной статье содержится информация о индейки постнатальном онтогенезе в продуктах питания.

Ключевые слова: индейк, рацион, комбикорм, кукурузно и костная мука.

KURKALAR POSTNATAL ONTOGENIZIDAGI OZUQA RATSIONNING BERILISHI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kurkalarning postnatal ontogenezida kerak boladigan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari haqida ma'lumot yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kurka, ratsion, kombikorma, makka va suyak uni.

Introduction. The need for poultry meat among the population is increasing year by year. Per capita consumption of poultry in the world is 58 kg in Belarus, 29.4 kg in Russia, 26.9 kg in Ukraine, and in the Republic of Uzbekistan this indicator has been increasing in recent years. because poultry meat and eggs are dietary products and are an important food source for the human body [4].

The body weight of 42-day-old broilers in meat poultry farming reaches 2.5 kg. At the same time, breeders pay attention to the early growth rate of young animals, the shape of the meat body, the quality of meat and the size of muscle fibers. However, breeding activities aimed at increasing the growth rate of broiler body weight often do not take into account the processes of bone tissue formation and its mineralization, which leads to a decrease in physiological reserves and provides ample opportunities for the manifestation of genetic potential [1].

Keeping and feeding turkeys. Turkeys are raised on the ground in thick beds, cages and camps (groups under shelter). When growing turkeys in thick beds on the ground, the room is disinfected, and the walls of the building are whitewashed with lime. Slaked lime is laid on the floor surface of the rooms with a thickness of 2-4 cm, and wood shavings, straw, straw, crushed corn stalks, rice husks are laid on it with a thickness of 5-6 cm. This method is convenient for use in small poultry farms where turkey meat products are grown [2]. The use of one or another breeding method depends on the breed and crosses of turkeys used in the farm. Light and medium-weight turkey crosses are well adapted to growing in cages. Heavy turkey breeds are grown indoors in thick beds, in most cases in summer camps [3].

Result. The composition of chicken feed prepared for turkey chicks does not differ from the composition of chicken feed. However, in order to meet the protein requirements of turkey chicks, the proportion of grain, vegetable and animal proteins in the soft feed prepared for them is significantly changed. The composition of the soft feed prepared for turkey chicks up to 30 days old

contains 40-45% grain feed, 17-22.5% animal feed, 18-20% animal feed, 7% skim milk, 6-9% yeast, o t flour 4-7% and vegetable oil 5%.

Grain, dehulled barley and oats, cotton, soybeans, and pellets are passed through the galvir to reduce the amount of klechatka in the dry fodder. In addition to dry milk and fish meal, (processed) poultry feathers are used as a source of protein and amino acids. The amount of crude protein in chicken feed for 30-60-day-old turkey chicks is reduced, and the level of metabolic energy is increased. The amount of cereal food is increased by 55-60%, and animal food is reduced to 12-18%. Cereal foods in the dry feed of turkeys older than 60 days are reduced to 60-65%, and animal foods to 15-17%. 120-day-old turkey chicks are fed with grain feed 68-72%, corn and meal 6-10%, animal feed 5%, yeast 3-5%, grass meal 7-15%, and mineral feed 3- It should be 5%.

In the absence of solid feeds, mixed feeds are used to feed chicks. In the first 10 days, it can be mixed with skim milk, fish oil, meat and bone meal, boiled eggs, and yogurt. During the initial growing period, green grass is replaced with green onions, later with chopped green grass, eggs, cooked meat and fish scraps. Until the age of 45 days, only wet mixed food is fed, and up to 10 days, feeding should be done every 3 hours.

Summary. One-month-old turkeys should be fed up to 5 times a day. Liquid mixed feed should be completely consumed by turkey chicks within 30-40 minutes. From the age of 45 days, cereals are added to the mixed feed. It is very important to have enough mangers and water troughs when raising turkey chicks. When feeding dry food, turkeys up to 120 days old should have a manger and water trough not less than 4 cm wide per head, 6 cm wide at 120-180 days old, and 10-12 cm wide when fed wet mixed food.

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